

APPENDIX

Appendix 2: Research Questionnaire

The Influence of Human Factors on Emergency Decision-Making through the Mediation of Situational Awareness: A Study of Control Room Operators in the Oil and Gas Industry

Confidentiality and Ethics Statement

This questionnaire is part of an academic research project. All information you provide will be kept strictly confidential and used solely for research purposes. Your responses will not affect your personal or professional status in any way. We sincerely appreciate your participation.

Please provide your answers by selecting the option that best represents your condition.

Use the following 5-point Likert scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

SECTION A. DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. Name :
2. Gender : Male Female
3. Age :
 < 25 years 26–35 years 36–45 years 46–55 years ≥ 56 years
4. Nationality :
5. Highest Education Level
 High School / Vocational School DIPLOMA Bachelor's (S1)
 Master's (S2) Doctorate (S3)
6. Years of Experience in the Oil and Gas Industry:
 < 5 years 6–10 years 11–15 years ≥ 20 years
7. Years of Experience in the Control Room
 < 2 year 2–5 years 6–10 years ≥ 10 years
8. Have you ever been directly involved in an emergency situation in the control room?
 Yes No
9. Frequency of Involvement in Emergency Decision-Making:
 Often Rarely Never

SECTION B. PERTANYAAN PENELITIAN

JOB STRESS

- | | | | | | |
|---|----------------------------|----------------------------|----------------------------|----------------------------|----------------------------|
| JS1. I feel that my workload exceeds my capabilities. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS2. I often have to handle multiple tasks simultaneously in emergency situations. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS3. I struggle to complete important tasks because I have to manage many things at same time. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS4. Instructions from my supervisor are often unclear and inconsistent. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS5. In emergency situations, I do not know who has the authority to make decisions. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS6. Work procedures during emergencies are often unclear and confusing. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS7. I find it difficult to think quickly and accurately when operational conditions change suddenly. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS8. I feel unable to make calm decisions when the available information is limited. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS9. I easily lose focus in high-pressure and high-risk work situations. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS10. My relationship with team members is often disrupted during operational tasks. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS11. Differences in work styles between shifts often lead to conflict due to poor communication. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |
| JS12. In critical situations, I often do not receive enough support to handle problems. | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5 |

FATIGUE

- F1. I feel exhausted after completing long working hours in the control room. 1 2 3 4 5
- F2. I find it difficult to maintain focus when experiencing physical discomfort such as aches and pains. 1 2 3 4 5
- F3. I often feel tired while performing activities in the control room. 1 2 3 4 5
- F4. I struggle to stay focused while carrying out tasks in the control room. 1 2 3 4 5
- F5. I am less responsive to changes in operational conditions when the work feels monotonous. 1 2 3 4 5
- F6. I find it difficult to choose the right action even in simple situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- F7. I do not get enough sleep duration before starting work. 1 2 3 4 5
- F8. My sleep quality is poor, making it hard to accurately understand operational situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- F9. I often feel drowsy during working hours, which slows down my responses. 1 2 3 4 5
- F10. In emergency situations, my reaction to signals or commands tends to be slow. 1 2 3 4 5
- F11. I am less accurate in reading system information when working in a fatigued state. 1 2 3 4 5
- F12. I am less alert to potential hazards while working. 1 2 3 4 5

COMPETENCY

- C1. My understanding of SOPs helps me make the right decisions during critical conditions. 1 2 3 4 5
- C2. I am able to identify operational risks before taking action. 1 2 3 4 5
- C3. I understand the functions and usage of all instruments in the control room. 1 2 3 4 5
- C4. My ability to operate the system supports effective decision-making during emergency conditions.. 1 2 3 4 5
- C5. I am able to make accurate and timely decisions when facing abnormal operational conditions. 1 2 3 4 5
- C6. I can quickly identify and analyze root causes when operational disturbances occur. 1 2 3 4 5
- C7. I comply with all safety instructions when dealing with high-risk operational situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- C8. I carry out tasks with great attention to detail to avoid operational errors. 1 2 3 4 5
- C9. I take initiative to find solutions before operational problems escalate into emergencies. 1 2 3 4 5
- C10. I am able to connect control system data to gain a comprehensive understanding of the situation. 1 2 3 4 5
- C11. I am able to objectively evaluate various alternative solutions before making a decision. 1 2 3 4 5
- C12. I can identify logical or judgment errors that may affect operational decisions. 1 2 3 4 5

SITUATIONAL AWARENESS

- SA1. I can recognize alarms and system indicators that signal changes in operational conditions. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA2. I am able to identify potential hazards before the situation becomes critical. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA3. I notice small changes in system parameters that may have a major impact in emergency situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA4. I am able to interpret the meaning of data and signals displayed by the control system. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA5. I am able to integrate information from various sources to gain a comprehensive understanding of operational conditions. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA6. I am able to prioritize work steps according to the level of risk and urgency of the operational condition. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA7. I can anticipate the consequences of the current situation before taking action. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA8. I can recognize patterns or trends in system data to anticipate potential risks. 1 2 3 4 5
- SA9. I use my understanding of operational conditions to plan the next course of action. 1 2 3 4 5

TRUST IN AUTOMATION

- TIA1. The system behaves transparently and provides clear information. 1 2 3 4 5
- TIA2. I feel confident in the intentions, actions, and outputs of the system. 1 2 3 4 5
- TIA3. I can use the system with confidence without unnecessary worry. 1 2 3 4 5
- TIA4. The system operates safely and does not create harmful consequences. 1 2 3 4 5
- TIA5. The system makes me feel safe and secure when using it. 1 2 3 4 5
- TIA6. The system demonstrates integrity and consistently follows proper rules. 1 2 3 4 5
- TIA7. The system is reliable and supports me in making accurate decisions during emergencies. 1 2 3 4 5

EMERGENCY DECISION MAKING

- EDM1. I am able to make important decisions within a short time when facing emergency conditions. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM2. I can still make accurate decisions even under high pressure. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM3. I can quickly choose the most appropriate course of action in emergency situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM4. I am able to maintain the quality of decisions even under pressure or high stress. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM5. I am able to control my emotions so they do not interfere with the decision-making process. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM6. I am able to avoid fatal mistakes even when required to make quick decisions. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM7. I consistently apply SOPs, checklists, or protocols when facing emergency situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM8. I am able to execute standard procedures quickly and accurately when operational conditions change suddenly. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM9. I understand how supporting technologies work and use them optimally in high-pressure situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM10. I am able to evaluate the impact of my initial decisions in emergency situations. 1 2 3 4 5
- EDM11. I do not cling to my initial decisions if the situation indicates a different course of action. 1 2 3 4 5
- SP12. I use experiences from previous decisions to improve the quality of future decisions. 1 2 3 4 5